

The viscometric measurements of *S*-substituted triazinothiocarbamides at various compositions

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Abstract : *S*-Triazino and thiocarbamido nucleus containing drugs have their own importance, significance and identity in the organic, drug, pharmaceutical and medicinal chemistry since from last four decades. Therefore, viscometric measurements of newly synthesized drugs viz. 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*o*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_1), 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*m*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_2) and 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_3), were carried out at various percentage compositions of solvent to investigate effect of structure, group on *S*-triazinothiocarbamides. The data and result obtained during this investigation gave detail information regarding drug absorption, transmission, activity and effect of these drugs. Taking all these things into consideration this research work was carried out.

Keywords : 1-(4-Hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*o*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_1), 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*m*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_2), 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_3), viscometric measurements.

Introduction

Viscosity is internal friction of the liquid. Viscosity measurements play an important role in pharmaceutical, medicinal and drug chemistry¹⁻³. In drug chemistry viscometric studies provides an important and useful information regarding solute-solute, solute-solvent, solvent-solvent interactions. The drug absorption, transmission, activity and effect will directly related to viscosity measurements of the solute (drug) and solvent interactions in the human anatomy because the pharmacokinetics of drugs can be described on the viscometric study. Hence, taking all these things into consideration and as wider programme of this laboratory in the synthesis of nitrogen, sulphur and nitrogen and sulphur containing heteroacycles and heterocycles, it was thought interesting to carry out the viscometric measurements of newly synthesized drugs in this laboratory. This study explores the potency of synthesized drug, stability of drug and also renovates and modifies the traditional drugs which are used by medi-

nal practitioner.

The pharmaceutical and medicinal literature survey clearly indicated that newly synthesized drugs are the best for particular diseases but after some time interval, the drug effect and their activities become less and those drugs became out dated for that disease, due to continuous evolutions in the pathogens. It was observed that in the universe these pathogens have a great and rapid evolutionary phenomenon and the drug become food for those pathogens. It become challenge to chemist and researchers to synthesized new type drugs for old diseases.

S-Triazino and thiocarbamido nucleus containing drugs create its own identity and significance in drug and pharmaceutical chemistry⁴⁻¹⁰. Hence for studying the potency of recently synthesized drugs in this laboratory, the viscosity measurements of 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*o*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_1), 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*m*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_2) and 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_3) were studied at various per-

centage compositions. This study becomes milestone in the drug medicinal, pharmaceutical of triazinothiocarbamides.

Experimental

All the chemicals used of A.R. grade and doubly distilled water was used. Weighing was made on Mechaniki Zaktady Precyzyjnej Gdansk balance made in Poland (± 0.001 g). Densities of solutions were determined by a bicapillary pycnometer ($\pm 0.2\%$) having a bulb volume of about 10 cm^3 and capillary having an internal diameter of 1 mm and calibrated with deionised doubly distilled water. The accuracy of density measurements were within $\pm 0.1\text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The viscosities were measured by means of Ostwald’s viscometer thoroughly cleaned and dried. The viscometer was kept in Elite thermostatic water bath and temperature variation was maintained at $30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (± 0.1) for each measurements, sufficient time was allowed to attain thermal equilibrium between viscometer

and water bath. As Ligands L_1 - L_3 were synthesized in this laboratory by Tayade’s researcher group so only chemical characteristics, nitrogen and sulphur estimations were performed and the spectral analysis are not carried out as these are gifted by researcher group of Tayade.

Observations and calculations :

The present study deals with the viscosity investigation of Ligand (L_1), Ligand (L_2), Ligand (L_3) in 60%, 70% and 80% dioxane-water mixture at different compositions and at 303.15 K ($30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The data obtained have been used to compute molecular interactions in terms if β -coefficient of different ligands. The viscometric readings were taken as described in literature¹¹. The results obtained was mentioned in Tables 1-9.

According to Jone’s-Dole equation, $(\eta - 1)\sqrt{C} = A + \beta\sqrt{C}$ at different concentration and different percentage. A and β -coefficient values calculated and are enlisted in Tables 10-12.

Determination of relative and specific viscosities at different concentrations :

(A) For Ligand L_1 :

Table 1. Dioxane-water (60%) : Temp. 303.15 K , System L_1 , Medium : dioxane-water

Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density $\rho \times 10^3$	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31628	371	1.0238	1.5530	0.5527	1.74843
0.075	0.27389	359	1.0236	1.4986	0.4985	1.81992
0.056	0.23668	344	1.0232	1.4403	0.4403	1.86019
0.042	0.20497	335	1.0229	1.3988	0.3987	1.94499

Table 2. Dioxane-water (70%) : Temp. 303.15 K , System L_1 , Medium : dioxane-water

Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density $\rho \times 10^3$	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31625	396	1.0289	1.4179	0.4179	1.32121
0.075	0.27388	387	1.0282	1.3791	0.3791	1.38392
0.056	0.23666	374	1.0273	1.3338	0.3339	1.41015
0.042	0.20496	364	1.0258	1.2969	0.2968	1.44776

Table 3. Dioxane-water (80%) : Temp. 303.15 K , System L_1 , Medium : dioxane-water

Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density $\rho \times 10^3$	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31625	414	1.0315	1.3804	0.3804	1.20262
0.075	0.27388	403	1.0294	1.3413	0.3413	1.24586
0.056	0.23666	393	1.0282	1.3054	0.3054	1.29014
0.042	0.20497	385	1.0266	1.2791	0.2791	1.36139

(B) For Ligand L₂ :

Table 4. Dioxane-water (60%) : Temp. 303.15 K, System L ₂ , Medium : dioxane-water						
Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density 9×10^3	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31625	393	1.03393	1.6609	0.6609	2.08934
0.075	0.27388	376	1.02946	1.5819	0.5819	2.12445
0.056	0.23666	372	1.02612	1.5218	0.5218	2.20418
0.042	0.20495	349	1.02182	1.4695	0.4695	2.28997

Table 5. Dioxane-water (70%) : Temp. 303.15 K, System L ₂ , Medium : dioxane-water						
Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density 9×10^3	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31625	426	1.03501	1.5316	0.5316	1.68044
0.075	0.27388	408	1.03103	1.4619	0.4619	1.68588
0.056	0.23666	398	1.02592	1.4185	0.4185	1.76766
0.042	0.20497	391	1.02074	1.3879	0.3879	1.89229

Table 6. Dioxane-water (80%) : Temp. 303.15 K, System L ₂ , Medium : dioxane-water						
Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density 9×10^3	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31625	418	1.0357	1.4069	0.4069	1.28612
0.075	0.27388	415	1.0315	1.3835	0.3836	1.39999
0.056	0.23666	408	1.0263	1.3598	0.3598	1.52087
0.042	0.20495	398	1.0227	1.3236	0.3236	1.57805

(C) For Ligand L₃

Table 7. Dioxane-water (60%) : Temp. 303.15 K, System L ₃ , Medium : dioxane-water						
Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density 9×10^3	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31625	474	1.03602	2.0082	1.00812	3.18759
0.075	0.27388	473	1.03303	1.99785	0.99785	3.64358
0.056	0.23666	449	1.02902	1.88423	0.88422	3.73645
0.042	0.20495	432	1.02404	1.80274	0.80274	3.91689

Table 8. Dioxane-water (70%) : Temp. 303.15 K, System L ₃ , Medium : dioxane-water						
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0.1	0.31625	488.06	1.03874	1.76441	0.76442	2.41727
0.075	0.27388	470.19	1.03342	1.69113	0.69113	2.52362
0.056	0.23666	451.53	1.02902	1.61701	0.61703	2.60733
0.042	0.20495	443.32	1.02573	1.58227	0.58227	2.84257

Table 9. Dioxane-water (80%) : Temp. 303.15 K, System L ₃ , Medium : dioxane-water						
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0.1	0.31625	499	1.0397	1.67582	0.67581	2.13709
0.075	0.27388	481	1.0359	1.60967	0.60967	2.22615
0.056	0.23666	469	1.0315	1.56392	0.56392	2.38292
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(B) For Ligand L₂ :

Table 4. Dioxane-water (60%) : Temp. 303.15 K, System L ₂ , Medium : dioxane-water						
Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density 9×10^3	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
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S-Triazino and thiocarbamido nucleus containing drugs create its own identity and significance in drug and pharmaceutical chemistry⁴⁻¹⁰. Hence for studying the potency of recently synthesized drugs in this laboratory, the viscosity measurements of 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*o*-tolylthiocarbamide (L₁), 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*m*-tolylthiocarbamide (L₂) and 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (L₃) were studied at various per-

centage compositions. This study becomes milestone in the drug medicinal, pharmaceutical of triazinothiocarbamides.

Experimental

All the chemicals used of A.R. grade and doubly distilled water was used. Weighing was made on Mechaniki Zaktady Precyzyjnej Gdansk balance made in Poland (± 0.001 g). Densities of solutions were determined by a bicapillary pycnometer ($\pm 0.2\%$) having a bulb volume of about 10 cm^3 and capillary having an internal diameter of 1 mm and calibrated with deionised doubly distilled water. The accuracy of density measurements were within $\pm 0.1\text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The viscosities were measured by means of Ostwald’s viscometer thoroughly cleaned and dried. The viscometer was kept in Elite thermostatic water bath and temperature variation was maintained at $30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (± 0.1) for each measurements, sufficient time was allowed to attain thermal equilibrium between viscometer

and water bath. As Ligands L_1 - L_3 were synthesized in this laboratory by Tayade’s researcher group so only chemical characteristics, nitrogen and sulphur estimations were performed and the spectral analysis are not carried out as these are gifted by researcher group of Tayade.

Observations and calculations :

The present study deals with the viscosity investigation of Ligand (L_1), Ligand (L_2), Ligand (L_3) in 60%, 70% and 80% dioxane-water mixture at different compositions and at 303.15 K ($30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The data obtained have been used to compute molecular interactions in terms if β -coefficient of different ligands. The viscometric readings were taken as described in literature¹¹. The results obtained was mentioned in Tables 1-9.

According to Jone’s-Dole equation, $(\eta - 1)\sqrt{C} = A + \beta\sqrt{C}$ at different concentration and different percentage. A and β -coefficient values calculated and are enlisted in Tables 10-12.

Determination of relative and specific viscosities at different concentrations :

(A) For Ligand L_1 :

Table 1. Dioxane-water (60%) : Temp. 303.15 K , System L_1 , Medium : dioxane-water

Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density $\rho \times 10^3$	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31628	371	1.0238	1.5530	0.5527	1.74843
0.075	0.27389	359	1.0236	1.4986	0.4985	1.81992
0.056	0.23668	344	1.0232	1.4403	0.4403	1.86019
0.042	0.20497	335	1.0229	1.3988	0.3987	1.94499

Table 2. Dioxane-water (70%) : Temp. 303.15 K , System L_1 , Medium : dioxane-water

Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density $\rho \times 10^3$	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31625	396	1.0289	1.4179	0.4179	1.32121
0.075	0.27388	387	1.0282	1.3791	0.3791	1.38392
0.056	0.23666	374	1.0273	1.3338	0.3339	1.41015
0.042	0.20496	364	1.0258	1.2969	0.2968	1.44776

Table 3. Dioxane-water (80%) : Temp. 303.15 K , System L_1 , Medium : dioxane-water

Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density $\rho \times 10^3$	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31625	414	1.0315	1.3804	0.3804	1.20262
0.075	0.27388	403	1.0294	1.3413	0.3413	1.24586
0.056	0.23666	393	1.0282	1.3054	0.3054	1.29014
0.042	0.20497	385	1.0266	1.2791	0.2791	1.36139

(B) For Ligand L₂ :

Table 4. Dioxane-water (60%) : Temp. 303.15 K, System L ₂ , Medium : dioxane-water						
Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density 9×10^3	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31625	393	1.03393	1.6609	0.6609	2.08934
0.075	0.27388	376	1.02946	1.5819	0.5819	2.12445
0.056	0.23666	372	1.02612	1.5218	0.5218	2.20418
0.042	0.20495	349	1.02182	1.4695	0.4695	2.28997

Table 5. Dioxane-water (70%) : Temp. 303.15 K, System L ₂ , Medium : dioxane-water						
Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density 9×10^3	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31625	426	1.03501	1.5316	0.5316	1.68044
0.075	0.27388	408	1.03103	1.4619	0.4619	1.68588
0.056	0.23666	398	1.02592	1.4185	0.4185	1.76766
0.042	0.20497	391	1.02074	1.3879	0.3879	1.89229

Table 6. Dioxane-water (80%) : Temp. 303.15 K, System L ₂ , Medium : dioxane-water						
Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density 9×10^3	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31625	418	1.0357	1.4069	0.4069	1.28612
0.075	0.27388	415	1.0315	1.3835	0.3836	1.39999
0.056	0.23666	408	1.0263	1.3598	0.3598	1.52087
0.042	0.20495	398	1.0227	1.3236	0.3236	1.57805

(C) For Ligand L₃

Table 7. Dioxane-water (60%) : Temp. 303.15 K, System L ₃ , Medium : dioxane-water						
Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density 9×10^3	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31625	474	1.03602	2.0082	1.00812	3.18759
0.075	0.27388	473	1.03303	1.99785	0.99785	3.64358
0.056	0.23666	449	1.02902	1.88423	0.88422	3.73645
0.042	0.20495	432	1.02404	1.80274	0.80274	3.91689

Table 8. Dioxane-water (70%) : Temp. 303.15 K, System L ₃ , Medium : dioxane-water						
Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density 9×10^3	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31625	488.06	1.03874	1.76441	0.76442	2.41727
0.075	0.27388	470.19	1.03342	1.69113	0.69113	2.52362
0.056	0.23666	451.53	1.02902	1.61701	0.61703	2.60733
0.042	0.20495	443.32	1.02573	1.58227	0.58227	2.84257

Table 9. Dioxane-water (80%) : Temp. 303.15 K, System L ₃ , Medium : dioxane-water						
Conc.	\sqrt{C}	Time flow t (s)	Density 9×10^3	η_r	$\eta_{sp} = \eta_r - 1$	$\eta_r - 1/\sqrt{C}$
0.1	0.31625	499	1.0397	1.67582	0.67581	2.13709
0.075	0.27388	481	1.0359	1.60967	0.60967	2.22615
0.056	0.23666	469	1.0315	1.56392	0.56392	2.38292
0.042	0.20495	454	1.0276	1.50984	0.50984	2.48769

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The viscometric measurements of *S*-substituted triazinothiocarbamides at various compositions

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Abstract : *S*-Triazino and thiocarbamido nucleus containing drugs have their own importance, significance and identity in the organic, drug, pharmaceutical and medicinal chemistry since from last four decades. Therefore, viscometric measurements of newly synthesized drugs viz. 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*o*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_1), 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*m*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_2) and 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_3), were carried out at various percentage compositions of solvent to investigate effect of structure, group on *S*-triazinothiocarbamides. The data and result obtained during this investigation gave detail information regarding drug absorption, transmission, activity and effect of these drugs. Taking all these things into consideration this research work was carried out.

Keywords : 1-(4-Hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*o*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_1), 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*m*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_2), 1-(4-hydroxy)-*S*-triazino-3-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (L_3), viscometric measurements.

Introduction

Viscosity is internal friction of the liquid. Viscosity measurements play an important role in pharmaceutical, medicinal and drug chemistry¹⁻³. In drug chemistry viscometric studies provides an important and useful information regarding solute-solute, solute-solvent, solvent-solvent interactions. The drug absorption, transmission, activity and effect will directly related to viscosity measurements of the solute (drug) and solvent interactions in the human anatomy because the pharmacokinetics of drugs can be described on the viscometric study. Hence, taking all these things into consideration and as wider programme of this laboratory in the synthesis of nitrogen, sulphur and nitrogen and sulphur containing heteroacycles and heterocycles, it was thought interesting to carry out the viscometric measurements of newly synthesized drugs in this laboratory. This study explores the potency of synthesized drug, stability of drug and also renovates and modifies the traditional drugs which are used by medi-

nal practitioner.

The pharmaceutical and medicinal literature survey clearly indicated that newly synthesized drugs are the best for particular diseases but after some time interval, the drug effect and their activities become less and those drugs became out dated for that disease, due to continuous evolutions in the pathogens. It was observed that in the universe these pathogens have a great and rapid evolutionary phenomenon and the drug become food for those pathogens. It become challenge to chemist and researchers to synthesized new type drugs for old diseases.

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(B) For Ligand L₂ :

Table 4. Dioxane-water (60%) : Temp. 303.15 K, System L ₂ , Medium : dioxane-water						
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(C) For Ligand L₃

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